

The East European Socialist/Post-socialist City as a Comparative Endeavor: Rethinking Our Research Perspective

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Abstract

Eastern Europe has been portrayed as the West's undeveloped "other" since the French Enlightenment. In this brief debate article, we argue that Eastern Europe's marginalization has only been augmented, even if inadvertently so, in scholarly debates on the "socialist city" and the "post-socialist city." Explicitly or implicitly, both debates use Western cities as a "natural" point of comparison and as examples of a more advanced type of urbanism. This approach has led to systematic underappreciation of the specific and sometimes positive aspects of East European urbanism. The article calls for a renewed engagement with East European cities in which they are studied on their own terms, rather than in perpetual comparative dependency on their Western counterparts.

Keywords

Socialism, post-socialism, Eastern Europe, epistemic marginalization, comparative urban studies

Introduction

It is sometimes asserted that urbanists¹ have not fully embraced international comparison as a research strategy (e.g., Dear, 2005, Pierre, 2005, Robinson, 2011). In this debate article, we challenge this assertion and propose that research pertaining to the cities of Eastern Europe—the subject matter of this special issue—not only has been almost exclusively comparative but has been almost *too* comparative. Scholars (one co-author of this article included) have largely shied away from exploring the rich and complex dynamics of East European cities in their *own right*. Rather, we seem to have taken an easier route: investigating East European cities to make them understandable to Western audiences through relentless comparison with their perceived "sister cities," which are located primarily in Western Europe and to a lesser extent, elsewhere in the collective West. We believe this comparative impulse was likely driven by an aspiration to legitimize the East European city as

¹ By urbanists, we mean primarily scholars in architectural history, urban geography, planning, and sociology—the disciplines most of our own work fits in.

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a worthy subject of research. However, it may have produced the opposite effect by implicitly suggesting that taken on their own terms, without a Western comparative component, East European cities are too obscure or too ordinary to warrant the pages written on them. This exercise of constant comparison is contributing to the epistemic marginalization of Eastern Europe. It is solidifying this region's intellectual dependency on the West and obscuring the positive aspects of East European urbanism that could have been instructive to Europeans across the continent and to others, had they been better recognized.

To advance this point, we use Charles Tilly's (1984) influential typology of comparative research. Tilly identified four fundamental comparative research strategies (see also Brenner, 2001, 136-138, Robinson, 2011, 5-12). One strategy is individualizing comparisons: comparisons that highlight the specific aspects of a case study that distinguish it from others. Another is variation-finding comparisons, which draw attention to contrasts between individual cases, thereby explaining variation, but variation situated within a system. Encompassing comparisons position similarities or differences between cases in terms of their relationship to a system. Finally, there are universalizing comparisons: comparisons that establish that every individual instance of a phenomenon follows essentially the same system-wide rules. The boundaries between the four strategies are not set in stone, and it is not always obvious where on Tilly's scale a particular research approach falls.

Here, we use Tilly's framework as a lens through which to frame the two major debates on cities in Eastern Europe after World War II: debates about the East European city during the period of state socialism (1945-1989) and debates about the East European city after the collapse of state socialism (1990-present). It seems comparative attempts to study the East European city during socialism tended to be variation-finding, whereas those addressing the East European city after socialism tended to be encompassing. Individualizing comparisons have been rare but more common in the case of the socialist city, whereas universalizing comparisons have been almost entirely missing. The concern with these approaches is twofold: First, the variation-finding and encompassing comparisons undercut the study of potentially important specific characteristics of the East European city. Second, the comparisons have almost always been unidirectional: While East European cities are almost always placed in the Western context, Western cities are immune from such treatment. The latter, apparently, are worth studying on their own merits.

Before we proceed, a couple of caveats. First, since this paper is a "debate article," it is very brief. It does not include a comprehensive analysis of the literature. Rather, the argument is made primarily by revisiting a small sampling of some of the best-known works on the "socialist city" and the "post-socialist city" published in English. A systematic review of the vast literature on both subjects is beyond the scope of this essay.

Second, when discussing the various types of comparisons, we mean comparisons that involve the cities in Eastern Europe as a group rather than comparisons focused on any

particular city in Eastern Europe. In other words, we are not critiquing the literature for neglecting to pay sufficient attention to the unique characteristics of say, Belgrade or Bratislava (although this may be a valid point, too). Rather, we are critiquing the literature for treating the entire category of cities in Eastern Europe as too insignificant on their own, so as to put them in perpetual comparative dependency on the cities of the collective West. Yet we acknowledge that grouping East European cities (or other phenomena) together is a broad, potentially reductionist generalization. Eastern Europe—understood here to include the European countries (and their successor states) that were considered socialist between 1945 and 1989—is a complex amalgam of nations with different histories, cultures, economies, and political structures. All were, often for long durations, either absorbed in or dominated by their more powerful neighbors to the North (e.g., the Russian Empire), South (the Ottoman Empire), or West (the German Empire, the Habsburg Empire). Even when not formally part of empires, in modern history East European nations have often been political and economic satellites whose fate was determined well outside of their borders—a situation that appears reflected in their subservient position in the urbanist literature as well.

The West's idea of Eastern Europe as its inferior other is much older than socialism. Yet it was not always there. Larry Wolfe's (1994) now-classic monograph *Inventing Eastern Europe* famously posited that the image of a backward East was first seriously propagated during the French Enlightenment. This "othering" was, in his view, an invention, as over the previous millennium, including all through the Renaissance, Europe's wealth and power were concentrated not in the West but in the South. If anything, it was the North—not the East—that historically had been less developed. But once the conceptual leap of portraying Eastern Europe as the less-deserving cousin was accomplished, it persisted and was only amplified during both the socialist and the post-socialist periods².

The remainder of this essay is organized as follows. First, we interpret late-20th-century debates on the "socialist city" as predominantly variation-finding. Next, we assess early 21st-century debates on the "socialist" and the "post-socialist city" as predominantly encompassing, in Tilly's terminology. We suggest that each approach inadvertently bolstered Eastern Europe's image as the West's immature European neighbour. In conclusion, we argue that urban scholars should consider an alternative path.

The Socialist City

Roughly between 1970 and 2000, the literature focused on the deceptively simple question: Is there a "socialist city" in Eastern Europe? Did East European cities during state socialism include spatial features that were sufficiently different from the features of cities in

² Wolff's point on the "invention" and subsequent marginalization of Eastern Europe have been critiqued and expanded upon by many authors since, from Maria Todorova (1997) to Ivan Kalmar (2022). On the complex relationship between East Europe's socialism and global colonial history, see Karkov & Valiavicharska (2019).

capitalist Western countries to warrant the conception of the socialist city as an autonomous entity? Equally importantly, were the processes of spatial production sufficiently distinct?

These debates on urban form and its production were grounded in broader debates about the nature of state socialism as either a distinct socio-economic regime or a subpart of Western-led industrial modernity. Two basic competing views were advanced, one grounded in the ideas of the so-called historical school and one in those of the so-called ecological school³. In line with the historical school tradition and following Henri Lefebvre's (1974) thesis that each political regime produces its own space, authors like Manuel Castells (1977) for example, assumed that if political regimes and economies are different, as they demonstrably were in socialist and capitalist contexts, then these regimes' main spatial products—in our case, the socialist city and the capitalist city—would be best understood as separate constructs⁴. The ecological school, which included authors such as Leo van den Berg et al. (1982), asserted that stages of urban development apply universally and depend mainly on the level of economic development. In this view, 20th-century urbanization was a function of two primary forces: modernization and industrialization. Therefore, although there were differences between socialist and capitalist cities, both as social processes and as spatial products, they paled in comparison to the similarities (e.g., growth in industrial functions, rising land-use specialization in cities, proliferation of standardized methods of construction).

These broad theoretical propositions were brought to light in empirical works on the East European city such as French and Hamilton's very well-known volume *The Socialist City: Spatial Structure and Urban Policy* (1979). This volume presented a diverse collection of in-depth essays on individual East European cities, pairs, and whole national urban systems, generally supporting the ideas of the historical school. However, even in this excellent compilation that looked at the socialist city as a distinct type and as a worthwhile study on its own, most chapters explicitly or implicitly used Western cities as a necessary point of reference. For instance, in a very interesting chapter on Soviet cities, authors Thomas Reiner and Robert Wilson felt compelled to explain that "comparison of Soviet experience with similar phenomena in the United States helps to clarify the issue" (Reiner and Wilson, 1979, p. 49). And in another chapter, on Warsaw, Grzegorz Weclawowicz felt necessary to start with: "Though it is a widespread twentieth-century phenomenon, urbanization exhibits marked international and regional differentiation. That the process is more or less complete in highly

³ The historical and the ecological schools advanced theories on urban development not just in Europe, but worldwide. Our point here is that these theories were applied to understanding socialist cities.

⁴ Castells (1977, p. 64) put it this way: "the relation between society and space (for that is what urbanization is) is a function of the specific organization of modes of production that coexist historically (with a predominance of one over the others) in a concrete social formation, and of the internal structure of each of these modes of production." Key differences in the processes of spatial production included the following: In socialist cities, the state had a near-monopoly on development (because it had nationalized most of the urban land, real estate, and production means). Land and property markets were less important, and the structure of cities was heavily impacted by the efforts of socialist regimes to create a highly industrialized and ostensibly classless society (e.g., through investing heavily in large-scale manufacturing and building uniform mass housing).

developed nations like the U.K. or U.S.A. is evidence of “counter-urbanization,” a trend towards lower levels of urban concentration. But in most nations, urbanization is still in embryo or in “full swing” (Weclawowicz 1979, p. 387). Note that this statement grants Western urbanism (or perhaps Western sub-urbanism) a “highly developed” status, whereas that in Poland, whose cities in the 1980s were compact, is portrayed as urbanism that is catching up.

As one of the authors in the French and Hamilton’s volume critically acknowledged in a later book, the main objective of the work on socialist cities often seemed to be not so much to advance understanding of socialist, East European urbanization itself but to enrich understanding of Western, capitalist urbanization (Harloe, 1981). The potential specificity of East European urbanism, as exhibited in features such as compact form, primacy of public space, and relatively equalitarian socio-spatial structure, was interesting only insofar as it could be juxtaposed to Western experiences and shown to be an exception to the general rule of 20th-century capitalist urbanization. In other words, even works nominally focused on Eastern Europe were in fact, just like French and Hamilton’s, implicitly comparative: seeking to make the East familiar to Western audiences and present it as a peculiar, if sometimes “backward” variation of a broader Western-centred model.

Perhaps not surprisingly, if anyone was firmly maintaining the thesis of the socialist city as an autonomous model—a “sotsgorod,” as the abbreviated Russian term goes—these were the Soviet urbanists. For obvious ideological reasons, their general position was that the Soviet city was not just different, but better than the Western city, especially because of its “classless nature,” the primacy of public property and public space, and the lack of obvious forms of segregation and inequality. This is how the esteemed Soviet architect and planner Lev Ilyin (1975) imagined the benefits of socialist urbanism in a well-known tractate: “The basic aspect that differentiates the socialist city from the capitalist city is the thoughtful organization of all individual parts and elements. In the socialist city, there are no differences, as there are in capitalist cities, between the beautiful architecture of central areas and the marginal neighborhoods housing the urban poor and the working class. Another contrast is the utilization of the entire urban space for use by all people. A socialist neighborhood is a neighborhood that is a single organism (rather than a collection of individual houses, as it is in capitalist cities) with a wholly integrated public system of social and cultural services. Streets and squares allow for a rich civic life of scope and form unknown in capitalist cities.”⁵

Peculiarly, however, the most ambitious attempts to invent an ostensibly new, socialist city had dissipated with the demise of the Soviet avant-garde. As far back as 1931, Lazar Kaganovich—one of Stalin’s key allies who played a lead role in Moscow’s planning and

⁵ Translated from Russian by Sonia Hirt. In Russian, the text is: “Другим отличием социалистического города является приспособленность его частей и всего города в целом для общественного пользования всех трудящихся. Социалистические кварталы представляют единый организм (а не сочетание отдельных домов, как в капиталистических городах) с общественной системой культурно-бытового обслуживания населения. Улицы и площади являются местом проявления общественной жизни трудящихся в таких размерах и формах, каких капиталистический строй и его города не знают.”

construction at the time—posited that the debate on what the socialist city should be is unnecessary because cities that develop under the tenets of a socialist political economy should be considered socialist already, even if their spatial structure has to be yet fully reformed (Kaganovich 1931). Without realizing of course, Kaganovich was positing a thesis similar to that of later-day Western urbanists of the historical-school persuasion: that since Soviet cities followed different processes of spatial production, resulting from the distinct tenets of the Soviet political economy, they must be socialist regardless of the details of their physical form. The break with Stalinism did not threaten Soviet consensus on the distinctiveness and superiority of the socialist city. But as we can tell by the above quote from Ilyin, even the Soviet urbanists felt compelled to talk about their cities in language comparing them to the West, while their comparisons led to the opposite conclusion on which the better city alternative is.

The Socialist City After Socialism

Fast-forward to the 1990s, when state socialism has receded into the rear-view mirror. Once the initial shock from the abrupt fall of the once-invincible Soviet bloc wore off, it was easier to further conceptualize socialism as East Europe's brief and temporary deviation from the Western model. Jurgen Habermas (1990) called the velvet revolutions "rectifying revolutions"—revolutions that signalled the East's return to its natural (Western-led) fold. This position was embraced in one form or another by the most prominent East European political leaders at the time, including Mikhail Gorbachev and Vaclav Havel⁶.

As scholars began revisiting the question of the "socialist city" with new curiosity, having the benefit of a fresh perspective, the ideas of the historical school became less popular whereas those of the ecological school gained ground. From the perspective of the ecological school, the similarities between the capitalist city and the socialist one outweighed the contrasts since the key processes driving urban change (e.g., modernization, standardization, and industrialization) were present in both capitalist and socialist settings of the mid-to-late 20th century. Capitalist and socialist cities could be thus regarded as variations of the general model of modern industrial urbanity. Although socialism had made some difference in urbanism, as prominent sociologist Ivan Szelenyi acknowledged in "Cities under Socialism— and After" (1996), one of the most influential essays on the topic published at the time, the contrasts were a matter of degree rather than kind. Gyorgy Enyedi summarized it this way: "socialist urbanization (more precisely, urbanization of East Central European countries) was not a new model of urbanization. Rather, East Central European socialist countries replicated stages of a more generally applicable global process of urban development" (1996, p. 102). Commonalities, such as the expanding size of cities and metro-regions, the emergence of

⁶ Gorbachev, for example, sought to position Europe's East as an integral part of "our common European home." Havel saw 20th-century state socialism and capitalism as the twin legs of industrial modernity and believed that both East and West were moving away from industrial modernity in parallel.

functional separation in cities (i.e., the split of residential, commercial, industrial, and recreational districts), and the growing influence of mass-production construction methods, offset the differences between the East and the West in terms of urbanism. Where notable differences existed, these were perhaps only a matter of a temporal lag. East European cities, even if they had remained socialist, were on a pathway to acquiring the characteristics of their Western counterparts—but with a few years' delay, because the countries in which they were situated were developmentally behind the West by a couple of decades (Enyedi 1996, 1998). One way or the other, the question of the now-disappearing “socialist city” was that question which contrasted it with the “cities of the advanced capitalist world”—the archetypes of a more mature type of modern urbanism (Smith 1996, p. 71). Further, although socialist urbanism was rarely labelled as inferior openly, other, softly negative terms were in common circulation. Eastern Europe, we were told for instance, suffered from “under-urbanization” (Enyedi, 1996). And in contrast to the colourful, vibrant cities of the West, the East European urban scene was portrayed as boring and unhappy, constituting “depressing rows of blocks,” painted in dull “industrial shades of gray and brown” (e.g., Lizon, 1996, p. 104, Gelazis et al. 2009, p. 9).

I am citing these authors, some of them the most brilliant in the field and all with strong ties to the region, not to critique their conclusions but to highlight, once again, the pervasiveness of the idea that the proper way of thinking about East European cities was to automatically place them in comparison to Western cities. Even Szelenyi, who seemed interested in variation-finding, could not escape using the West as the obvious reference point. Asking the question “How much difference socialism made to urban development in Eastern Europe?,” as he did (Szelenyi, 1996, p. 286), begs another question: Difference from what? Clearly, from the West, as Szelenyi himself acknowledged.

The Post-Socialist City

The term “post-socialist city” took hold around the dawn of the new millennium and is still in broad use (Stanilov 2007). Several assumptions seemed to be embedded into it. First, the assumption that post-socialism exists as socialism once did—as a somewhat distinct historical condition with its own political and economic dynamics. Second, that the future is blurry enough that it is too early to come up with an original label for the present. Hence, it's best to name the present as something that it is *not* and something that comes *after* the past (as is the case of many other widely used terms: “post-Fordist,” post-industrial,” “post-modern,” “post-welfare-state,” etc.). And third, that the logical point of departure for studying the “post-socialist city” is its own recently departed self—the socialist city.

A logical goal of researchers was to determine how the political and economic processes of urban spatial production changed after 1990 and what the results were. For example, what in the basic structure of Prague or Tallinn is different in, say, the year 2000 versus the year 1980 or 1990, and what social, economic, or cultural developments led to this modified state

of affairs (e.g., Sykora 1999 and Ruoppila 2005)? Several empirically based answers about the changes from the socialist to the post-socialist city emerged, including increased socio-spatial segregation by class and ethnicity, intense urban sprawl, aggressive privatization and informalization of urban space, and growing aesthetic pluralism in lieu of socialist monotony—all changes in the physical fabric of the city resulting from the radical withdrawal of the public sector from urban development and the restitution and sale of public assets to private parties (Hirt and Stanilov, 2009).

One could claim that the term “post-socialist city” suggests specificity, distinction from the cities that were never socialist. Yet a closer look at its application shows that the Western-centered perspective did not go away; arguably, it became even stronger. The reference point for the new comparisons was as much the East European city’s old, socialist self as it was, once again, the Western, capitalist city. Whereas some of the most erudite authors seriously debated the nature of the post-socialist metamorphosis (e.g., Verdery, 1996, Stark and Bruszt, 1998, Pickles and Smith, 1998, Pickles and Unwin, 2004), others seem to have too easily settled on the term “transition” (e.g., Kornai, 1993, Hirt and Stanilov, 2009), which implied that Eastern Europe is moving toward a known point—Western-style capitalism—and therefore, its cities are becoming increasingly similar to Western cities.

East European cities, we were told, were never so different in structure from Western ones: they were always “more European than socialist” (Bertaud, 2006). If anything, they were now on their way “toward globalization,” as all others (Hamilton et al., 2005), toward becoming typical capitalist cities (Kovacs, 1999). They were undergoing “a steady rehabilitation of natural [read Western-like] urban development,” a process that socialism had stalled (Ouredníček 2005, p. 154), a “*revival* of urban processes which had been *interrupted* by forty years of socialism” (my emphasis) (Ouredníček and Temelova 2009, p. 9).

On occasion, East European cities were presented as experiencing processes identical to the processes in cities of the Western world, but with differences in the speed and intensity of change. Take for example a couple of the best-received in-depth monographs on national capitals. Bodnar’s study of Budapest (2001) and Hirt’s (i.e., one of the co-authors of this very essay) study of Sofia (2012) both tried hard to contextualize—i.e., “encompass” in Tilly’s terms—the experience of these cities as special cases of the broader shift from industrial to post-industrial, modern to post-modern urbanism—a trend already well-studied in major Western nodes such as London and Los Angeles. Bodnar specifically states that hers is an “*implicitly comparative approach*” (her emphasis): “while I focus on only one case—Budapest—in my analysis I aim to expose, and explore the implications of, the conceptual transferences from social scholarship (notably, in the West.)” (Bodnar 2001, p. 8). Similarly, Hirt sets up her task as follows: to contribute to the literature not just on post-socialism, but also on “modernity and post-modernity, and globalization and urbanization.” The claim here, too, is that the method is implicitly comparative (Hirt 2012, pp. 4-5). If any particular claim

could be made about the capitals of Hungary and of Bulgaria, it was that they are post-industrializing and post-modernizing more aggressively than the cities of the Western world. If under socialism East European cities were examples of modern urbanism delayed—Enyedi's 1990s thesis—now they were examples of urbanism accelerated, but accelerated toward a known, Western-like post-industrial, post-modern state. In other words, the East European deviation, its variation from the core Western model, was dissipating, and it was just a matter of time before Eastern cities “caught up” to Western ones.

As in the previous section, our point here is not to dispute whether these authors have reached the right conclusions—they very well might have!—but that they have tended to shy away from thinking about the East European city *without* placing it into a Western context. We suspect had they not taken a comparative approach, these authors may have never succeeded in getting their works published in English.

A Path Less Traveled

In her outstanding book *Ordinary Cities*, Jennifer Robinson (2006) posited that Western-based urban scholars have long divided the world into two categories: Western cities, which are assumed to be the “originators of urbanism,” and non-Western cities, especially those assumed to be in the “Third World,” whose main value appears to be providing a point of contrast with the West. Robinson argues that to enrich urban theory, we need to “post-colonize urban studies”: i.e., we need to extend “the post-colonial critique of social theory to the study of cities” and we need to envision cities outside the Western world as equally important “originators of urbanism” (Robinson, 2006, p. 1).

We believe that most authors who have sought to place East European cities, cities in the former “Second World,” just as those in the “Third World,” in relation to Western ones have done so with the noble intention of de-provincializing that perhaps too “ordinary” (in Robinson's terminology) half of Europe. Part of these authors' motivation may have been to make the region better known to Western audiences by using the vocabularies customary to the West.

Yet we also believe that the unfortunate, if unintentional, result of these efforts is to provincialize Eastern Europe further by positioning it as always “learning” from or “catching up” with the West. But why learn from the West and why *only* from the West? Keeping in mind the torturous modern history of Eastern Europe, which has been dominated by its Western neighbors for long stretches of time, it may be helpful to learn from cities in the post-colonial Global South, parts of which have been (or are still) socialist today. This approach has been sporadically suggested (Hladik, 2011, Sjoberg, 2014, Badescu, 2016), but has yet to flourish.

By placing the East European city in perpetual comparative dependence on the West, authors may have inadvertently aided policy-makers and politicians who over the last forty years have treated Eastern Europe—home to some of Europe's oldest nation-states, brightest

artists and intellectuals, and grandest capital cities like Budapest and Prague that were at some point seats of Europe's large empires—as a mere knock-off brand of the West.

Furthermore, today we know that urban features like compactness, reliance on public transit, and generosity of public spaces are key to sustainability and resiliency. These aspects of spatial structure were typical of East European cities during socialism but were lost in socialism's aftermath as these cities became, indeed, more Western. Perhaps if we urban scholars had focused on understanding and preserving these distinguishing features rather than on projecting their presumably inevitable downfall to fit into the Western mold, we could have advised those in power to put in the efforts required to keep these positive urban features so that the West of Europe could have learned from its Eastern neighbors as it should have.

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